

Meaning-Making and the Politics of Intergenerational Injustice in Jordan

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During conversations with young Jordanians, I used to ask what it was like to be young in Jordan today compared to what they imagined it was like for their parents' generation. One interviewee, Salim, said, "My dad had his education paid, went to his uncles to borrow a little money, opened his dentist clinic. It cost him JD 3,000 to get married; today, it's like JD 20,000. Back in the day, we had oil from Iraq, vegetables from Syria, and gas from Egypt." Another interviewee, Suleiman, said,

There was less competition (for the older generation), they could travel, they could do PhDs, not many people were starting businesses. They had little resources, but a lot of opportunities. We have all the resources—the phones, Google, everything is right here—but there are no opportunities! Back then, you had to go to a library to find anything, now it is right there. However, now, everyone wants to travel, everyone wants to create an app.

These testimonies indicate a simple socio-economic fact: because political-economic transformations unfold over time, the ebbs and flows of a country's economic growth socially elevate some generations who come of age during good times while prev-

enting others from flourishing. Young Jordanians today are an example of a generation that has gotten a raw deal. They have had to plan for their futures amid austerity, welfare state retrenchment, and the removal of subsidies, all of which has contributed to skyrocketing youth unemployment, later marriages, and dreams of migration. In contrast, older age groups face much lower unemployment rates, because they entered the labor market during better times and dominate the shrinking public sector and anemic private sector. While the total unemployment rate was 21% in late 2024, youth aged 15-24 faced an average unemployment rate of 46%. A young woman is more than four times as likely to be unemployed than an adult male (Tzannatos 2025).

This situation begs the question, what is the political impact of intergenerational economic injustice? Under what circumstances do the objective conditions of such injustices compel generations to politicize them, and when do young people remain quiescent? In this short essay, I argue that addressing these questions requires focusing not only on actual economic channels of opportunity but also on how young people ascribe meaning to them.

The literature on Arab politics has not been impervious to the entanglements between political-economic change and generationally-charged political agency. In particular, scholars have noted that intergenerational injustice was a pivotal antecedent to the Arab Uprisings (Achcar 2013, Bayat 2011, Singerman 2013). As Emma Murphy (2012, 7) described it, “economies with ever-wider disparities in income and wealth and restricted access to the social benefits of adulthood” led youth to “set themselves in opposition to an older generation, the generation of authoritarian rulers and those who brought them to power.” (15)

Yet, we know relatively little about the mechanisms that compel some generations suffering intergenerational injustice to shape into political collectives. As Ameni Mehrez and David Siddhartha Patel note in this volume, such analysis is further complicated by the difficulty of disentangling what constitutes a period effect (e.g., a *Zeitgeist*), an age effect (e.g., that youth are more impressionable than adults), or a cohort effect (e.g., that people who are in the same age group at the same time may share common outlooks or experiences). When approaching this question, I have discovered a surprising interlocutor in Norbert Elias, who is much less famous than his teacher Karl Mannheim for contributing to the study of generations. In one of his lesser-known works, *Studies on the Germans* (2013[1989]), Elias examined two 20th-century German youth movements—right-wing Weimar-era paramilitary groups and left-wing post-WWII terrorist groups. Both youth movements radicalized when older generations jammed up channels of upward mobility. Yet, the critical causal mechanism that politicized these cohorts was not objective life chances alone but what Elias called their “chances to meaning.”

When young officers were shut out of the military following Germany’s demobilization after World War I, instead of pursuing civilian careers, they opted to form so-called *Freikorps*, paramilitary volunteer units. According to Elias, the young officers recreated military prestige outside of the army because this “was the only meaningful job, a profession they understood and which gave them pleasure.” (189). Similarly, German socialist youth movements in the 1960s and '70s arose out of their perceived exclusion from politically meaningful institutions like universities and political parties. Elias notes that the grievances leading left-wing youth to mobilize “did not stem only from economic class contradictions... [but also from] ...the search for meaning, the search for a personally fulfilling purpose which can be experienced as meaningful,” (237).

From Elias’s study, we learn that to carry political salience, political actors must actively make intergenerational injustices meaningful. Many Jordanian youth are doing just that. For instance, in his satirical comic strips, cartoonist Emad Hajjaj situates youth immiseration in the context of the privileges enjoyed by older generations and political elites. In a cartoon that comments on the so-called “Unemployment Marches” of 2019, unemployed youth demanding jobs march past an older man who occupies five chairs labeled “Seats 1–5.” The old man, whose sheer size symbolizes unequal access to resources, beckons to one of the protestors while holding a sixth chair towards him and says, “Come over here... You made me very sad... and I’ve decided to donate to you one of my seats... Thankfully, I am still able to be generous.”

Figure 1. “The Unemployment Marches.” Reproduced with permission from the artist. Source: Hajjaj, Emad. 2019. “Masīrāt Al-’Ātilīn ‘an Al-’Amal” (“The Unemployment Marches”), Facebook. January 26. <https://www.facebook.com/AbuMahjoobNews/photos/a.327453017293610/2285825918122967/?type=3>.

Figure 2. Cartoon About Generations. Reproduced with permission from the artist. Source: Hajjaj, Emad. 2020. “Al-Ihsā’āt: Mu’dal Al-Batāla 19 percent fil-Urdun” (“Statistics: The Unemployment Rate Is 19 percent in Jordan”), Roya News. March 8. <https://royanews.tv/news/207887>.

In another of Hajjaj’s cartoons, four elderly men sit next to each other. The first three men exclaim, “Support youth,” “Employ youth,” and “Empower youth,” while the fourth man says, “Where did the youth go? They emigrated!” Hajjaj’s cartoons interpret generational cleavages as generational conflicts. He appeals to other youth, articulating how intergenerational injustices stem from the unfair hoarding of resources by older generations and political elites.

However, conversely, generational injustices can also be rendered less politically meaningful if dominant actors, like the Jordanian regime, frame generational injustices in a different way. In 2017, while addressing the UN General Assembly, Crown Prince Hussein said, “if our generation is trapped in a struggle between the tradition and mindset of the past, on the one hand, and the ways and technologies of the present, on the other, we will never move forward,” (MAAP Film

Productions 2017). In other words, according to Hussein, rather than focusing on generational conflicts, Jordanian youth must transcend the generational cleavage to be successful. In a different speech, the Crown Prince told youth, “it is your turn now to build, to increase Jordan’s progress and prosperity. However, in your own ways, and with the tools of your age, because *every generation has its own identity, opportunities, and challenges*,” (Royal Hashemite Court 2018, emphasis added).

This framing of youth’s economic conditions as filled with unique opportunities is not just talk. This vision is supported by an infrastructure of youth governance—government-operated NGOs, educational reforms, and national campaigns—that encourages youth to perceive their generation as uniquely positioned to take on the challenges of their time (Almqvist 2023). As scholars, focusing our attention on meaning-making will enable us to better comprehend how this struggle over generational injustices will unfold in Jordan and the broader Middle East. ♦

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